

1 DESCRIPTIVE DATA AND CORRELATIONS BETWEEN VARIABLES OF INTEREST

Table 1 shows descriptive data on the variables included in the analysis and correlations between them.

Table 1: Means and standard deviations of and correlations between variables of interest

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.
1. Gender	-								
2. Age	-.19**	-							
3. Worrying	.25**	-.32**	-						
4. IU	.20**	-.37**	.77**	-					
5. Content	.02	-.09	.07	.15*	-				
6. Usability	-.04	.03	-.03	.04	.64**	-			
7. Aesthetic	-.01	.01	.03	.10	.73**	.60**	-		
8. Revisit	-.05	.02	-.01	.06	.77**	.53**	.64**	-	
9. Recommend	-.02	.04	-.02	.06	.73**	.52**	.58**	.92**	-
<i>M</i>	-	50.65	42.50	43.17	4.43	5.23	4.55	3.38	3.46
<i>SD</i>	-	13.49	13.60	15.70	1.23	1.28	1.48	1.61	1.83

Notes. ** indicates a correlation is significant at $p < .01$. *** indicates a correlation is significant at $p < .001$. IU \equiv intolerance of uncertainty. Scales for the respective variables are: 3. PSWQ; 4. IUS; 5. Web-CLIC; 6. PWU-G; 7. VisAWI-S; 8. + 9. Behavior Intention. Gender is dummy coded with 0 representing male participants and 1 representing female participants.

2 MODEL PARAMETERS

Table 2 shows the model parameters elaborating Figure 1 in the original study. Several indices attest to the model's the satisfactory fit: A chi square test for exact model fit is not significant as is preferred ($\chi^2(14, N = 395) = 21.19, p = .10$). An RMSEA of .036 indicates a good fit as it is lower than .06. This conclusion is added upon with CFI (= .997) and TLI (= .991) both exceeding the suggested cutoff of .95. The SRMR of .029 is also below the recommended value of .05. Therefore the model is deemed to fit the data well.

Table 2: Model parameters (standardized)

Regression on/correlation with	Estimate (β)	Standard Error	Two-tailed <i>p</i> -value
Age on			
Intolerance of uncertainty	-.35	.05	<.001
Worrying	-.03	.03	.46
Gender on			
Intolerance of uncertainty	.13	.05	<.01
Worrying	.10	.03	<.01
Intolerance of uncertainty on			
Worrying	.74	.03	<.001
Content	.24	.08	<.01
Usability	.17	.08	.03
Aesthetic	-.11	.08	.16
Content on			
Intention to revisit	.66	.05	<.001
Intention to recommend	.66	.05	<.01
Aesthetic on			
Intention to revisit	.16	.05	<.01
Intention to recommend	.10	.05	.052
Usability with			
Content	.62	.06	<.001
Aesthetic	.59	.06	<.001
Intention to revisit	.01	.02	.65
Intention to recommend	.04	.03	.14
Content with			
Aesthetic	.71	.06	<.001
Intention to revisit with			
Intention to recommend	.34	.03	<.001

Note. Gender is dummy coded with 0 representing male participants and 1 representing female participants.